

Measures for quality-assured service portfolio management in NFDI4Objects

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I. Introduction and current status

NFDI4Objects (N4O) is dedicated to research data management for the study of material heritage from more than three million years of human history. Together with the communities from various disciplines, the consortium develops standards for object-related data, develops software applications and data repositories in accordance with the FAIR and CARE principles, and drafts concepts for norm data and guidelines for sustainable data storage.

An important goal is to guarantee sustainable quality assurance in line with the above-mentioned objectives for the diverse services that are being developed in N4O and provided by the consortium or, in some cases, by its partners, thereby ensuring reliable and interoperable data services. To this end, the existing governance structures in N4O must be supplemented by a structured service portfolio management, which ensures that the range of services is operated on a permanent level with regard to N4O's quality requirements. To this end, the N4O steering committee convened a working group in 2024 and tasked it with developing a proposal for a corresponding concept and steering framework. Following discussions within the consortium, this was approved by the steering committee and is now binding for all services offered by N4O.

The concept is largely based on standards developed by NFDI4Biodiversity for the same purpose¹. This means that N4O not only draws on a steering framework that has proven itself against the backdrop of very similar needs and requirements. Above all, NFDI4Biodiversity refers to the ITIL framework, which ensures that N4O service portfolio management also follows established best practice rules for resilient, efficient and, above all, quality-oriented IT service management. In order to meet the specific needs of N4O, adjustments were made primarily with regard to community-related services, which form a special focus in the N4O service portfolio, as explained below.

The N4O service portfolio management is based on the following core elements:

1.) Binding terminology that guarantees the common cross-consortial understanding of the terms that are relevant for the certification process (*Appendix 01*).

In addition to services that are broadly understood to be technical in nature, community-based services, which form a substantial part of the N4O service portfolio, are described in an additional service class. This applies to all services that organise and moderate a permanent, structured discourse within a community for the development and continuous updating of standards and best practices

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8327366>

forming the basis for technical implementations. The other components of the N4O service portfolio management then refer to this service class and its characteristics accordingly.

2.) A standardised registration form that serves as the basis for subsequent certification process (*Appendix 02*).

The registration form is standardised so that each service is described with the same level of detail and all relevant information is collected in the same way. On this basis a certification decision is then made. Here, too, the special characteristics of community-based services are taken into account. It should be noted that the service definitions differ from the terminology used in the N4O application. The reason for this is that simplified schemes based on established service terms are intended to simply filling out the form. For internal monitoring, however, an additional assignment to the categories used in the application must be made.

3.) A steering framework that describes the organisational setting within N4O and regulates both the organisational structure (i.e. roles and tasks) and the service certification process (onboarding, monitoring, i.e. recertification, offboarding, etc.) (*Appendix 03*).

The key unit is primarily the steering committee, being responsible for the overall strategic development and ensuring the compliance with the “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft and FAIR principles. Secondly the service monitoring team organises and oversees the certification process together with the coordinator, who also acts as quality assurance officer. Another body, the *Community Cluster Service Portfolio Development*, is responsible for developing proposals for decisive N4O service quality criteria, which are then approved in the regular N4O Commons process. Ultimately, the Certification Board makes the certification decision based on these quality criteria defined for N4O.

4.) A Community Cluster "Service Portfolio Development" (CC), which – as described above – develops proposals for the quality criteria².

While other consortia had already during the application phase provided comparable units in their governance structure (see, for example, the Special Interest Group in NFDI4Biodiversity with comparable tasks), there exists currently no adequate body within N4O. Thus, during the current funding period, a Community Cluster has been initiated for this purpose and will assume this function.

II. Implementation and outlook

As mentioned above, the terminology, the registration form and the steering framework have been approved and are therefore binding; the CC for formulating the quality criteria has been established and has begun its work. All actors who wish to provide services within the framework of N4O have described their services with the necessary information required in the registration form. As soon as the first binding quality criteria have been accepted by the consortium, the certification and the official onboarding of services will start.

With the existing steering committee of the N4O consortium and its spokesperson – capable of acting as managing director in accordance with the aforementioned steering framework – an essential body is already fully operational. The remaining bodies envisaged by the above-described concepts will shortly be established, or the relevant actors will be appointed by the steering committee. To keep N4O’s governance structures lean, existing organisational units should be broadly involved wherever possible. That is, the bodies will – where appropriate – recruit members from subsets of the Coordination Office, the Task Areas, or the Technical Unit.

² https://www.nfdi4objects.net/portal/ccs/cc27_nfdi4objects_dienstportfolio_management/.

To date, no procedural framework comparable to rules of procedure has been established, which would provide concrete guidelines for implementing the processes outlined in the steering framework. Should a need for such rules of procedure become apparent during the work of the CC, the CC may either develop appropriate proposals on the recommendation of the steering committee, or delegate the drafting to a Temporary Working Group.

Likewise, a technical solution must be introduced to enable a simple and efficient management of the regular monitoring process, ensuring that these procedures remain as streamlined as possible in terms of sustainable, long-term operation.

Furthermore, the N4O service portfolio management concept, once implemented, will be subject to ongoing evaluation through a supporting monitoring process during the remainder of the project's duration. Based on the evaluation results and taking into account developments across the entire NFDI landscape, the consortium or the steering committee will decide, following this assessment, which elements should be incorporated into the governance structure of any potential follow-up proposal.